

Using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Tools in the Teaching and Learning Through the Lens of Teachers

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Abstract. This study unearthed teachers' experiences using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools in teaching and learning in Libungan West District, Cotabato Division. This study investigated how teachers used information and communication technology (ICT) tools for teaching and learning in Libungan West District, located in the Cotabato Division. Ten (10) public school teachers were designated to participate in the study. This study used a phenomenological approach through virtual in-depth interviews. Thematic analysis revealed obstacles such as restricted availability of ICT resources, insufficient training, and connectivity problems, underscoring educators' continuous endeavors to adjust to diverse online platforms despite their restricted ICT proficiency and the difficulty of unstable internet connections for both educators and students. However, the study's public-school teachers used coping strategies like effective time management, cooperation, and self-training. They showed tenacity and flexibility by being prepared to modify their approach. Learning outcomes were positively impacted by teachers working together. Both teachers and students found comfort and convenience in using tools and technology. The study's conclusions highlighted how crucial peer mentoring, capacity building, and collaboration were for educators.

KEY WORDS

1. information communication technology tools 2. learning 3. peer mentoring

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1. Introduction

In this digital age, integrating Information and Communication Technology in the classroom is critical for providing students with the skills they will need in the twenty-first century. The swift progression of technology has revolutionized the field of education, so much so that teachers must adopt ICT tools to improve the quality of instruction. Using ICT in education is about allowing students to acquire, apply, and master the critical skills needed in today's connected and rapidly changing world—it's not

just about keeping up with technology trends.

Effective use of information and communication technology (ICT), which includes computers, the internet, television, storage devices, and mobile phones, is critical for improving the teaching and learning process. However, its integration faces common challenges for educators, such as insufficient infrastructure, limited access to resources, resistance to change, and insufficient training. Educational institutions can help teachers by prioritizing professional devel-

opment, improving infrastructure, and creating an innovative environment. Addressing these barriers not only helps teachers navigate ICT more effectively but also improves the overall educational experience for students. ICT has emerged as a cornerstone of modern education, profoundly impacting school teaching and learning practices. Its importance lies in its ability to enhance learning experiences by providing interactive and engaging educational tools such as computers, tablets, and educational software. Through ICT, students access a vast repository of digital resources, including e-books, online journals, and educational videos, transcending the limitations of traditional textbooks. Moreover, ICT facilitates personalized learning experiences tailored to individual student needs, fostering autonomy and mastery of concepts. By promoting collaboration and communication through online platforms and collaborative tools, digital technology cultivates a dynamic learning environment where students can exchange ideas and work together on projects. Furthermore, integrating ICT in schools equips students with essential 21st-century skills such as digital literacy, critical thinking, and effective communication, preparing them for future academic and professional endeavors (Hassan Mizra, 2020). Additionally, ICT helps bridge the digital divide by ensuring equitable access to technology, empowering students from all backgrounds to thrive in a digital society. ICT enhances teaching practices by enabling educators to create interactive lesson plans, track student progress, and collaborate with peers. In essence, the importance of ICT in schools lies in its capacity to enrich learning experiences, foster skill development, promote inclusivity, and prepare students for success in an increasingly digital world. Educational institutions' adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) is conceived as an interconnected environment that enables student digital learning (Chen, 2020). ICTs help learners make informed decisions

and adopt responsible measures for the integrity of the environment and the economy's viability. This link fosters a quality, comprehensive, and transformative education that affects content and learning outcomes.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—Due to ICT's importance in society as well as in the future of education, identifying the possible challenges to integrating these technologies in schools would be an important step in improving the quality of teaching and learning. On the other hand, sustainable education from the perspective of ICT contributes to social transformation, enabling students to transform themselves and the societies in which they live. In the age of rapid technological advancement, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has become a global imperative. As Kosmutzky and Nokkala (2020) stated, however, in Nigeria, this integration faces multifaceted challenges, hindering the nation from reaping the full benefits of ICT in the educational sector. This essay delves into the issues surrounding ICT in Nigerian schools and proposes solutions to bridge the digital gap. One of the primary challenges impeding the effective integration of ICT in Nigerian schools is the lack of adequate infrastructure. Many schools across the country lack access to reliable electricity, internet connectivity, and functional ICT tools such as computers and tablets. Without these fundamental resources, efforts to incorporate ICT into the curriculum remain futile. Additionally, the digital divide between urban and rural areas exacerbates this issue, with rural schools bearing the brunt of infrastructural inadequacies (Krammer et al., 2018). In the Philippines, cutting-edge technologies, such as ICT in the classroom, are essential to giving students the chance to get the knowledge they need to function in the information age. It has been established how important it is to incorporate enough ICT tools into the teaching and learning. There has been a contention that

traditional learning settings and instructional methods fall short of adequately preparing students to work in a variety of settings in the current technological age (Hero, 2023). Students are better prepared to face future developments based on proper understanding when information and communication technology is taught and integrated into educational institutions. As a school ICT coordinator, integrating Information and communication technology in the teaching-learning process fosters student motivation and participation in learning important skills and concepts, allows teachers to effectively attain lesson objects as well as aids teachers in teaching topics deemed to be difficult, and helps students in the inculcation of 21st-century skills (Dela et al., 2020). Particularly in Libungan West District, teachers found it difficult to integrate ICT tools into their lessons due

to a lack of resources, which made it difficult to implement the technology and integrate it into the curriculum. These restrictions include a lack of projectors and computers, two pieces of necessary hardware, and erratic internet access, which is necessary to use online learning materials. In addition, many teachers felt unprepared and overburdened because they did not receive the professional development opportunities or training they needed to use ICT in the classroom.

1.2. Research Questions—The study wants to explore teachers' experiences using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools in teaching and learning in Libungan West District, Cotabato Division. Specifically, this study ought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the challenges faced by teachers in integrating ICT tools in teaching and learning in the Libungan West District, Cotabato Division?
- (2) How do teachers in the Libungan West District cope with limited ICT resources and infrastructure in their teaching practices?
- (3) What strategies do teachers employ to overcome the barriers to ICT integration in their classrooms?
- (4) What impact does the use of ICT tools have on student engagement and learning outcomes?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The essential terms were described operationally: Information and Communication Technology (ICT): refers to various tools and resources used to communicate, create, disseminate, store, and manage information. These include computers, the internet, television, storage devices, and mobile phones. ICT Tools: Specific technologies and applications such as educational software, multimedia presentations, virtual simulations, and online learning platforms like Google Classroom. Peer Mentoring: A support system where experienced teachers assist their colleagues in using ICT tools, sharing best practices, and troubleshooting issues. Collaboration: Joint efforts among teachers, students, parents, and commu-

nity stakeholders to improve the use of ICT in education. Capacity Building: Activities and initiatives aimed at enhancing teachers' skills and knowledge in using ICT tools. Professional Development: Continuous training and education for teachers to improve their ICT competencies and adapt to technological advancements. Digital Literacy: The ability to use digital tools and technologies effectively for various purposes. Learning Management Systems (LMS): Online platforms that facilitate the administration, documentation, tracking, reporting, and delivery of educational courses. Challenges in ICT Integration: Obstacles faced by educators in incorporating ICT tools into their teaching practices. Coping Mechanisms: Strategies and

practices employed by teachers to manage and overcome challenges in using ICT tools.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature—

1.4.1. *Technology Infrastructure*—A lack of infrastructure is a major challenge for teachers integrating ICT in their practices, particularly in developing countries. Inadequate infrastructure, such as intermittent internet and outdated hardware, causes frustration and discouragement among teachers (Barakabitze et al., 2019; Albirini, 2020).

1.4.2. *Teachers' Experiences with ICT Tools*—Teachers' experiences with ICT vary based on technology availability, professional development, and pedagogical beliefs. Positive outcomes include increased student engagement and improved learning efficiency (Karsenti Fievez, 2019). However, challenges such as limited access to technology and student resistance to new methods remain (Ertmer et al., 2019).

1.4.3. *Limited Network Access*—Inadequate network access, particularly in rural areas, hinders the effective use of ICT in education. Unreliable internet disrupts lessons and limits the use of digital resources, exacerbating educational disparities (World Bank, 2020; Akyol Erten, 2019; Tomaro, 2018).

1.4.4. *Inaccessibility of ICT Resources*—Many teachers struggle with new ICT tools due to insufficient resources, training, and support. Equitable distribution and investment in ICT resources are crucial (Hinostroza, 2018; Koehler Mishra, 2019).

1.4.5. *Lack of Effective Training*—Without comprehensive ICT training, teachers struggle to use technological tools effectively, resulting in frustration and missed opportunities for student engagement (Gnambs, 2021; Taimalu Luik, 2019; Rodriguez et al., 2019).

1.4.6. *Interactive and Engaging Methods*—ICT tools enable interactive and personalized learning, fostering student engagement and deeper understanding. Gamification and adap-

tive learning systems are particularly effective (Li et al., 2019; Hwang et al., 2019; DeWitt et al., 2019).

1.4.7. *Access to Diverse Resources*—ICT tools provide access to diverse educational materials, promoting inclusive and differentiated instruction. Open Educational Resources (OERs) reduce costs and support collaboration among educators (Alzahrani Oztok, 2019; Lahti Matikainen, 2019; Huang et al., 2019).

1.4.8. *Remote Learning Opportunities*—ICT tools facilitate remote learning, providing flexibility and accessibility, especially during global events. These tools ensure educational continuity and promote inclusive education (Hodges et al., 2020; Barbour LaBonte, 2020; Heffernan et al., 2019).

1.4.9. *Self-Training and Support*—Teachers improve digital literacy through online courses, webinars, and forums. This self-directed learning is essential for adapting to limited ICT accessibility (Hodges et al., 2019).

1.4.10. *Alternative Strategies*—In the absence of reliable internet, teachers use offline digital resources and asynchronous communication platforms. Schools can provide shared devices and local networks to support technological integration (Cardullo et al., 2021).

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study was anchored on Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. Koehler and Mishra (2009) stated that a teacher depends on three domains of knowledge for the effective integration of ICT into teaching and learning: content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and technological knowledge (TK). The TPACK framework recognizes that effective technology integration requires the intersection of all three domains—CK, PK, and TK. Teachers must draw upon their content knowledge to identify learning objectives, pedagogical knowledge to design instructional strategies, and technological knowledge to select and use appropriate technologies (Koh, 2011). Additionally,

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

TPACK emphasizes the dynamic interplay between these domains, highlighting the importance of thoughtful integration and ongoing reflection on teaching practices. By developing TPACK, teachers can enhance their ability to leverage technology to support student learning, engagement, and achievement across various disciplinary areas and educational contexts. This integrated approach to teaching with technology promotes meaningful learning experiences and prepares students for success in a digital world (Thompson, 2021). Teaching with technology is complicated further when the challenges newer technologies present to teachers are considered. In our work, the word technology applies equally to analog and digital, as well as new and old, technologies. As a matter of practical significance, however, most of the technologies under consideration in current literature are newer and digital and have some inherent properties that make applying them straightforwardly difficult. Most traditional pedagogical technologies are characterized by specificity a pencil is for writing, while a microscope is for viewing small objects; stability like pencils, pendulums, and chalkboards have not changed

a great deal over time; and transparency of functions such as the inner workings of the pencil or the pendulum are simple and directly related to their function. Over time these technologies achieve a transparency of perception; they become commonplace and, in most cases, are not even considered to be technologies. Digital technologies—such as computers, handheld devices, and software applications—by contrast, are protean (usable in many different ways), unstable (rapidly changing), and opaque (the inner workings are hidden from users) (Turkle, 1995). Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework and serves as the schemata of the study. This research investigated the teachers’ experiences of using ICT tools in teaching processes and their coping mechanisms. These two themes were working themes that would lead to the development of Insights drawn from the teachers’ experiences and challenges of using ICT tools in teaching and learning. In this study, the Venn Diagram shown exemplifies the connectivity between the experiences of teachers, how teachers cope with challenges, and the possible insights gained from the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection and analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is

appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) are optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research—selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend the research paradigms as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, “ultimate or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2018), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the teachers’ narratives, as they utilized ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes, were elaborated on since ICT infrastructure and implementation in the school is a vital factor in the effective delivery of the curriculum. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants’ answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the participants’ responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. It was concerned with the nature and the scope of knowledge. Simply put, it was concerned with how people come to know something and how people know the truth. It addresses the following questions: What counts as knowledge? How are knowledge claims justified? What is the relationship between the researcher and what is being researched? (Creswell Poth, 2018). I would identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The purpose of this research was to gather important details on the teachers’ narratives regarding the use of ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes, particularly in Libungan West District, Cotabato Division. The researcher assured us that close interaction with the participants would be established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the teachers’ narratives as they used ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. Axiology, on the other hand, refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discussed values that shape the narrative and included their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. According to axiology, the researcher should be transparent about the values that influence the story and provide both his and the participants’ interpretations (Gupta, 2018). The researcher upholds the dignity and value of every detail of information

obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserves the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interprets the answers in the light of the participant's interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study context, the researcher used the first person to explain the teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes and thoroughly discussed their responses during the interview. Leaving the philosophical discussion on the concept aside (Bitonti, 2020), a growing body of research investigates precisely this aspect, remarking on the importance of framing and rhetoric in taking the people in the audience by hand and accompanying them on a journey.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology aims to increase the credibility of the research by making the process transparent and reproducible. Your methodology should begin by describing your research question and the data type you used to answer it. You want to indicate why this type of data is appropriate, relevant, and essential to the question. In this study, the experiences and coping mechanisms of the teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes were unleashed from their narratives, specifically those coming from Libungan West District, Cotabato Division. The researcher's drive to understand the deeper meaning of the teachers' issues and challenges in using ICT tools in teaching and learning became the basis for qualitative research. The researcher's perception could be further defined by their specific viewpoint or worldview, which defines how they perceive that world (Creswell Poth, 2018). From the definition, Phenomenology is the inquiry method that deals with human

experience in which individuals perceive them as appearing to consciousness. Individuals share their lived experiences robustly when they go through that phenomenon. According to Merleau-Ponty, phenomenology is best related to essence, comprising not only perception but also unsoundness. Phenomenology was described as a rigorous, systematic, and critical analysis of an event. The prime purpose of this method is to explain the structure of the lived experience of an event. This methodological inquiry starts from phenomena of interest and aims to understand the subjective meaning of the lived experience of an event. The method was utterly based on the interpretive domain Estabrooks PA (2019).

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. With this in mind, the researcher must identify the problem of the study and establish a starting point from which the development of their framework and perspective would begin (Creswell, Poth, 2018). Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process.

2.4. Research Participants—Ten (10) informants participated in this study. The selected informants were from Libungan West District, Cotabato Division. All participants were junior high school teachers designated as school physical facility coordinators from nearby schools. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtain-

ing most or all of the perceptions would lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (2018) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There were no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. The qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, the formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy between researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise various ethical concerns. Qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, establishing honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. In this special issue, Fleming (2018) highlights some ethical dilemmas commonly encountered by an ‘insider researcher,’ including the power differential and ongoing relationships with participants. However, further consideration of the fundamentals of ethical research involving human participants was significant. In addition, for qualitative researchers, it is of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data were collected and how they were to be used. He also stated that informed consent was a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable subjects, except in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent was not possible and where it was felt that the benefits of the research outweighed the potential harm. A minimum requirement

for an interview study should be that written consent was obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions that were likely to be asked, the use to which the results were put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants’ utterances were used in reports. Participants should also be given time to consider their participation and ask the researcher questions. The researcher would follow ethical considerations in this study as part of the qualitative research process. The researcher was responsible for informing the participants entirely about the different aspects of the research in incomprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants’ potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results were published and used. Similarly, this study was submitted to the ethics committee of Rizal Memorial College, a graduate school, for verification and approval.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes, the explored experiences are fresh in the participant’s mind, whereas reliving past experiences may be difficult on other occasions. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher’s primary responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. The researcher interpreted ideas and responded based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher’s knowledge. Ex-

pert in Qualitative Methods. The researcher implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researchers addressed themselves and sought help from the research adviser and other professionals. These helped exhibit competence and explain the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of Data. The researcher ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before the data analysis can begin. Analyst of Data. The researcher saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensured that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. Organizer and Presenter of Data. The researcher presented the problem and the related literature and studies that supported it. Findings of the study were presented by research question, stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study.

2.7. *Data Collection*—According to Creswell and Poth (2018), “Whether we are aware of it or not, we always bring certain beliefs and philosophical assumptions to our research”. They influence how a researcher seeks information to answer the questions and serve as the basis for evaluating a study. Creswell and Poth’s (2018) assertion underscores the importance of becoming aware of these assumptions as they shape the research direction. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions must be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this infor-

mation, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interviews or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as inadequate data, prematurely leaving the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, the steps are followed in the data collection process. A letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Head, and the concerned teachers was prepared for easy data collection and was granted on January 25, 2024. All participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. Ten (10) informants were selected for this study. The selected teachers were considered individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the data collection. Data were collected from January 31 to February 15, 2024. The data storage on February 16, 2024, was made through a suggestion of Davidson (1996), where the database was used to back up information collected and note changes for all types of research studies. Limited data collection was engaged in this study.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a complete description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher’s personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. The researcher developed a list of significant statements. The researcher then found statements about how the individual was experiencing the topic, listed these significant state-

ments as having equal worth, and worked to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information called “meaning units” or themes. Writing a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon was next, followed by a description of “how” the experience happened. This is called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, the researcher wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating textural and structural descriptions. This passage was the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis was that it was a flexible method that could be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns were being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher knows exactly what he or she was interested in. No matter which type of study was being done and for what purpose, the most essential thing in the analysis was that the researcher respected the data and tried to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Mortensen, 2020).

Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using multiple methods to collect data on the same topic. It was a way of assuring the validity of research by using a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples and methods of data collection.

Environmental triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors, such as the time, day, and season of the

study. The idea was to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings were the same. The validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the results and findings of the research study depend on the researcher’s conduct. The trustworthiness of a research study was important in evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin his integrity. Transferability was described as how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings apply to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied mechanisms to maximize the utilization of ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narra-

tive. The information using the audit trail in this situation was thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Dependability was the extent to which the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher could use an inquiry audit to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings were consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of the database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references.

2.10. Analytical Framework—The data analysis plan used in this research study was Colaizzi's seven steps. Colaizzi's seven-step analysis method provides researchers with clear, logical, and sequential steps (Wirihana L, Welch A, Williamson M, et al 2021). This process of rigorous analysis provides a concise and thorough description of the phenomenon under study. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Transcripts were read repeatedly, significant statements, formulated meaning, cluster themes, developing exhaustive descriptions, producing the fundamental structure, and seeking

verification of the fundamental structure to extract thematic analysis. As cited by (Mohamad, 2022; Zaniel et al.,2023) The participants' responses were recorded, noted, and transcribed. The significant statements from the participants' responses were singled out as the basis of getting the code. (Mohamad, 2022). Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated to layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step was data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques, as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. This technique was useful to me in coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. It was also very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis Phase 1. Read and re-read all the transcribed interviews in order to make sense of them Phase 2. Extract significant statements. These are phrases or sentences that directly pertain to the investigated phenomenon Phase 3. The process of giving meaning to the statements. During the process, pertinent quotes are broadly categorized, subsequently, themes are generated based on multiple statements that convey similar meanings Phase 4. Repeat steps

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

1-3 for each interview then the researcher can begin to create themes based on the formulated meanings Phase 5. Compile an exhaustive description of everything generated in steps 1-4 Phase 6. Summarize the exhaustive description so that there was an identification of the fundamental structure of the phenomenon Phase 7. Credibility of the data was ensured through discussions with experts and independent reviewers

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter is enwrapped with the results accumulated from the lived experiences of elementary school teachers who ought to embrace new and innovative strategies to improve teaching and enrich the teaching and learning experience in schools through the utilization of ICT tools in teaching and learning. This chapter further discusses how they cope with the challenges of teaching using ICT tools. Presented also are the insights generated from the experiences of the public-school teachers. The themes brought about in achieving the objectives of this study were elaborated profoundly to provide clarity of the experiences. Before the discussion, the researcher would like to establish the symbols used as the researcher presents the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. Regarding the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the researcher also used codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. Lived experiences of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes—To better understand effective teaching and learning processes using ICT tools, we examined the composition of teaching practices through the lens of existing online learning research and identified the teacher roles needing stronger emphasis. This study ought to discover

how teachers adapt to new strategies in learning in diagnosing problems and needs among learners and in the teaching-learning process.

3.1.1. Challenges Encountered—Limited access to network connection. Many positive contributions to educational activities and processes. One of the implications of implementing e-education is the international network facility (Internet). The Internet has become an important tool for research and learning, allowing teachers and students to share and obtain information (Wibisono et al., 2023). Strong internet connectivity will allow for smoother and more reliable online learning experiences for both of them and could facilitate timely submission of the required data (Agayon et al., 2022). The participant's statement underscores frustration with inadequate internet infrastructure and connectivity issues hindering remote learning in their country. It highlights disparities in access to reliable online education due to unequal distribution of internet services, emphasizing the urgent need for equitable digital solutions to support inclusive education. Due to poor internet connection and microphone quality, the participant experiences audio issues during online teaching, resulting in distractions such as echo and background noise. Despite using headphones with built-in microphones, clarity remains poor, prompting colleagues to invest in separate microphones to improve instructional delivery. The participant raised the issue of students experiencing connectivity issues, which prevents them from attending online classes via video platforms. Even when the camera is turned off and only audio is used, low bandwidth or limited mobile data frequently prevent students from remaining in the virtual classroom and participating effectively. The findings of the study were confirmed by the pronouncement of SJ (2020) who expresses that the delivery of quality education is experiencing issues finishing the web work using ICT tools. It tends to be disappointing when a teacher is not prepared

for the conduct of online classes. Even though separation learning is to be sure muddled for understudies. Teachers need to manage the instructional resources for every class using ICT tools to make learning fast and easy both for the teacher and the learners. To equip themselves with the new normal education, the participants attend webinar sessions, watch video tutorials, and are mentored by peers. This allows them to widen their knowledge and develop useful skills as they design their instructional plans. Continuous learning provides growth and development of teachers as professionals, making them ready and prepared to embrace changes in the teaching landscape. Teachers play a significant role in improving the quality of education; hence, capacity building of teachers must receive top priority. ICT integration in education is influenced by many factors' barriers and enablers (Lawrence Tar, 2018). Toward this end, the study informed barriers or hindering factors affecting ICT integration include lack of resources, inadequate training, insufficient technical support, and lack of time. Other barriers include teachers' beliefs, visions concerning technology integration, and views about teaching, Akhmad Habibi, Rafiza Abdul Razak, Farrah Dina Yusop, Amirul Mukminin, Lalu Nurul Yaqin 1129 learning, and knowledge (Günes Bahçivan, 2018; Lawrence Tar, 2018; Marzulina et al., 2018). Some other studies informed barriers to ICT integration in education were conventional teaching culture, poor infrastructures, and limited human resources (Kilinc et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2013) It is a fact that the Philippines has a poor internet connection, far behind other countries the new normal in the delivery of education has been challenged. The participants of the study were not exempted from this. Teachers reasoned that this reality caused delays in implementing remote learning in general. Although internet plans can be accessed, they are not, however, created equal. Hence, this causes problems in classes using ICT tools. There is an unstable

internet connection even in urban areas, much more pressure on learners who live in remote places and find difficulty in using ICT tools in their assignments. They are forced to move to mountains or high places to get a bar or two (Valtonen et al., 2018). Inaccessibility of ICT resources – In the study by Kilinc et al. (2019), working with ICTs is often difficult because some ICTs are new for teachers. Social routines have to be built using ICT to meet new challenges and become alternative devices to replace old and conventional tools such as pens, paper, chalk, and boards. Teachers who attended training on how to make lesson episodes tended to do well in the virtual classroom and professed their newness to the task. They asserted that through training conducted at school and division level, they have got to know and understand how online teaching is done and the environment they will be in. They have implied that it is through watching videos of some common learning platforms in which students have access too. Learners are familiar only with the common social media platforms. Participant P2 talks about the early challenges of switching to online instruction for the first time, including integrating Google Classroom and other platforms. They consult curriculum standards and watch instructional videos to create engaging lessons and activities. In response to Participant P5's worries about obtaining materials and the possible results of their instruction, they show students instructional videos and acquaint them with widely used platforms such as Facebook, Zoom, and Messenger. However, training about online teaching and gathering resources are consequential in a way that it allures teachers to be ingenious in the delivery of learning which can alleviate the teacher's retained teaching practice and improve it to address the learning needs. Brought by the novelty of the task, teachers were challenged to prepare themselves for the delivery of quality education in a virtual classroom. Lack of effective training. Out of con-

sistency, teachers have experienced difficulty in instructional delivery because of the time and low preparedness of the teachers and learners as well. Both have limited knowledge and skills in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. The teaching pedagogy was changed, and the teachers were challenged on the methods of delivery to attain the objectives and maximize learning. This implied the increased need for capacitating teachers on the use of technology in instructional delivery. Moreover, the same result is parallel to the study conducted by Granthon (2020), which states that the same teachers heralded that putting up the most appropriate pedagogy to support the lesson in using ICT in the teaching and learning process creates another problem. Participants mentioned that doing inquiry-based learning is difficult as it requires guidance in the beginning stages. Most teachers claimed that blending the teaching strategy with distance learning modality should be established. Factors should be considered such as appropriateness, adequacy, and availability of resources. Technology supports and connects the two ends between strategy and modality; however, it should not overpower the design and delivery of the lessons. Rather, teachers should take advantage of technology but not neglect the learning design. It is understandable that ICTs are a recent innovation in the education systems of many countries, and therefore, many teachers still have no or little skill and experience in working with technologies, which may justify the limited ICT competence. The teachers' competence will remain a prominent challenge to the integration of ICT in education systems the world over until it is adequately addressed (Barakabitze et al., 2019).

3.1.2. Positive Effects—Interactive and engaging teaching methods – Respondents emphasized the benefits of using ICT tools in the classroom. They emphasized how these tools enable more dynamic and interactive lessons, which make learning more engaging for stu-

dents. Furthermore, ICT tools enable the incorporation of multimedia elements, resulting in a more comprehensive educational experience and catering to a variety of learning styles. The use of technology in the classroom has also been shown to increase student motivation and participation, resulting in a more effective learning environment. Incorporating ICT tools into the classroom has greatly improved teaching by making lessons more dynamic and engaging, thereby capturing students' attention and improving their learning experience. The incorporation of multimedia elements and interactive activities has significantly improved student engagement and motivation. Incorporating ICT tools into the classroom has greatly improved teaching by making lessons more dynamic and engaging, thereby capturing students' attention and improving their learning experience. The incorporation of multimedia elements and interactive activities has significantly improved student engagement and motivation. This notion is supported by research, which shows that ICT enables dynamic and interactive lessons that increase student engagement and motivation (Ertmer, 2015). According to research, multimedia elements such as photos, videos, and interactive activities cater to a wide range of learning styles, enriching the educational experience. Furthermore, the use of technology in education has been linked to improved academic performance and increased student participation, resulting in a more effective learning environment. Participants' perspectives are consistent with these findings, demonstrating how ICT tools play an important role in modern pedagogical practices aimed at improving student learning and engagement. Access to diverse resources - ICT tools enable a broader range of teaching methods, increasing instructional flexibility and adaptability. They add the benefit of accessing a global range of resources across multiple platforms and topics, enriching the curriculum. Teachers can incorporate a variety of materials, including videos, interactive simulations, and digital textbooks, to meet the needs of students with varying learning styles. This broad access to resources promotes a more inclusive and comprehensive educational experience for students. They appreciate how ICT tools allow them to use a broader range of teaching methods, which improves the diversity and effectiveness of their lessons. This diversity enables them to tailor their instruction to different learning styles and interests, ensuring that lessons are interesting and engaging. ICT tools facilitate global collaboration, enrich teaching with diverse perspectives, and stay current with educational trends, ensuring relevance and beneficial student learning outcomes. The teachers valued the diverse resources offered by ICT tools for a variety of reasons. One teacher emphasized how these tools enable seamless collaboration with educators around the world, allowing for the exchange of teaching materials and innovative ideas. This global connectivity enriches their teaching by incorporating different perspectives and methodologies, resulting in a more comprehensive educational experience for students. Another participant emphasized the importance of keeping up with the latest educational trends and research findings, which ICT tools enable. This keeps their teaching current and informed, incorporating cutting-edge knowledge into classroom practices to improve student learning outcomes. Teachers have access to a wide range of resources from multiple platforms, allowing them to incorporate current and relevant content into their lessons, catering to different learning styles and making lessons more engaging (Williams, 2020). Teachers can improve learning and teaching environments by reaching students in a variety of settings, including remote areas. This capability ensures that education is available to all students, regardless of geographical location. ICT tools enable teachers to provide lessons and resources to students who would otherwise be unable to attend

Fig. 3. The emerging themes of the experiences of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes

traditional classes. These tools contribute to closing the educational gap between urban and rural areas by enabling remote learning. Furthermore, remote learning options can accommodate a variety of learning schedules and needs, making education more adaptable and inclusive. The participant explains how ICT tools improve teaching by making lessons more interactive and engaging and thus capturing students' attention. It emphasizes the positive impact on students and teachers' overall learning experiences as well as their enjoyment of school. Teachers can improve learning and teaching environments by reaching students in a variety of settings, including remote areas. This capability ensures that education is available to all students, regardless of geographical location. ICT tools enable teachers to provide lessons and resources to students who would otherwise be unable to attend traditional classes. These tools contribute to closing the educational gap between urban and rural areas by enabling remote learning. Furthermore, remote learning options can accommodate a variety of learning

schedules and needs, making education more adaptable and inclusive. According to the participant, one significant advantage of ICT tools is their ability to provide real-time feedback, allowing teachers to respond to student questions and concerns immediately. This immediate communication promotes an efficient and responsive learning environment, ensuring that students are supported and engaged throughout the learning process. The responses from educators highlight the critical role of ICT tools in improving remote learning opportunities. For example, the ability to provide real-time feedback demonstrates how technology enables immediate interaction between teachers and students, which is critical in virtual education settings. This feature ensures that students receive timely assistance and clarification, even in remote settings where face-to-face interactions are limited. Teachers can stay up to date on current educational trends and provide relevant content that improves the quality of remote learning experiences by utilizing diverse ICT resources (UNESCO, 2020).

3.2. *Coping mechanism of teachers in using ICT tools In the teaching and learning processes*—second objective of this study is to ascertain the coping mechanism of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. The technologically inclined classroom is the venue for the delivery of learning in the 21st century. Informants discovered coping mechanisms of such endeavors were grouped into themes.

3.2.1. *Self-training and support*—They oftentimes manifested positive development inclining towards the future and hope. Resilience can be described as having a successful adaptation capacity to any difficult situation. The teacher showed great effort and thus became successful despite a compelling and menacing situation. The teacher-respondents overcame the difficulties and exhibited better development in the performance of their duties despite problems under high risk. with the proposition that characteristics that enable individuals to overcome difficulties and exhibit better development than the findings of the study conform expected to survival or the belief that they have a personal talent, despite problems under high risk. The resilient individuals show the ability to rapidly adjust in the face of stressful living experiences and are not easily deterred by difficulties or setbacks. The participants showed resiliency by doing the following activities positively such as the ability to learn new skills, ideas, and concepts, the ability to adapt to change and new situations, and healthy self-esteem. This means having a positive attitude about self-confidence when managing conflict. With resilience and adaptability, educators are navigating the challenges of incorporating ICT into their lesson plans. Participant P1 notes that using ICT can be stressful and challenging, but in order to perform at the best possible level in the classroom, it's important to respond positively to pressure and change. In a similar vein, Participant P2 talks about the initial stress of adjusting to new

teaching trends while still keeping a cheerful disposition and composed manner in spite of the heavy workload and frequent internet connectivity problems that have an impact on student attendance. Both participants show a commitment to effective teaching in the face of difficulties by highlighting their resolve and willingness to modify their methods to fit the demands of the modern learning environment. A need for support such as technical, pedagogical, and time management support arises since some teachers who are completely new to this new type of education may feel unprepared to enable instruction. With so much reliance on technology in today's schools, teachers are ill-equipped and incompetent. Given that it is a necessary skill for lifelong learning and a sought-after talent in industry, digital literacy must and should be practiced (Nilson, 2018). Additionally, Cardullo et al. (2021) noted that teachers were taken aback when required to provide emergency remote instruction due to a lack of computer literacy and expertise in distance education

3.2.2. *Openness to collaborate with others*—Collaboration within schools has, therefore, gained importance Krammer, M. (2018). Educational establishments are becoming more and more interested in collaborative learning approaches like team teaching, where instructors share knowledge and experiences, work together, and assist one another. When two or more teachers collaborate in some way throughout the preparation, execution, and/or assessment of a course or courses, it's known as team teaching. Undeniably, teachers are an adaptive group of people. People who tend to be high in the trait of openness are more willing to embrace new things, fresh ideas, and novel experiences. They are open-minded and approach new things with curiosity and tend to seek out novelty. They tend to pursue new adventures, experiences, and creative endeavors. They are also very good at thinking about and making connections between different concepts

and ideas. Openness is often viewed as a positive trait. Open people have a higher level of intrinsic motivation to pursue knowledge for its own sake. They are curious about the world and want to learn more about how it works. They are also eager to try new things, so they may be better able to adapt and thrive when faced with changes in their environment, situation, or relationships. This doesn't mean that openness doesn't have any downsides. Because people who are high on this trait seek novelty, they may also be more willing to engage in risky behaviors. Interestingly, however, some studies have linked decreased openness to increased risk for drug use. Teachers show a strong dedication to lifelong learning and flexibility in the face of an ever-changing educational environment, especially when it comes to technology and online resources. Participant P9 shows excitement for novel learning approaches that use technological tools. Similarly, Participant P10 emphasizes how teachers are always learning new things and how this helps them overcome obstacles in their line of work. Teachers who are receptive to new ideas and who never stop learning can keep up with the latest developments in education, which eventually helps both their students and the educational process.

3.2.3. Self-organization and Proper time management—The design of collaborative teacher partnerships and collaborative time should be designed in intentional ways that may support instructional improvement. For instance, organizing collaborative pairs among teachers who share teaching experiences, teachers who share a common planning time, and teachers who have identified instructional skills for improvement can potentially produce collaboration partnerships that engage teachers in effective and beneficial PD (professional development) (Carrol et al., 2021) Teachers have many opportunities to interact and work with their colleagues. Some can be formal, from job requirements for teachers in certain systems.

However, they can also be informal and voluntary interactions between colleagues triggered by situations or challenges teachers collectively feel the need to address (Ainley Carstens, 2018). Time management has always been an issue when it comes to load of work. In fact, people often miscarry responsibilities because of the lack of time. For teachers who manage to use ICT tools in the teaching-learning process, finding time is a very essential element in the process. Informants have acclaimed that by proper management of time, one can achieve the goals of effective delivery of the lesson, given the fact that this is very time-consuming, especially in the preparation of the instructional materials and assessment activities. It might be a hassle to fit through schedules, albeit this can still be achieved when one knows how to manage time effectively. Makes time. Informants of this study attested to the impact of time management. The participant focuses on daily learning in ICT and organizes their instructional materials according to the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) that their students need to master. They manage the schedules of eight classes to ensure that no class falls behind, and prepare lessons along with PowerPoint presentations and digital copies for students who may face connectivity issues. Despite the challenges of the new normal, teachers are exhibiting incredible dedication and adaptability in handling their workloads and incorporating ICT into their teaching practices. Participant P7 emphasizes the value of time management and their dedication to finishing assignments on schedule, even if it means staying up late to prepare course materials. Participant P8 emphasizes the importance of organization and setting priorities, especially when managing eight classes. To assist students with connectivity problems, they create lesson plans, PowerPoint presentations, and digital versions of the lessons. Participant P9 emphasizes juggling work and personal obligations, planning lessons in advance, and

Fig. 4. The emerging themes of the coping mechanism of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes

putting the needs of her students first during class. Comparably, Participant P10 talks about how hard it is to juggle housework and online instruction. However, he successfully manages his time by planning out his classes, grading, emails, and student communication in great detail. These observations highlight the teachers' proactive attempts to uphold high standards of instruction while adjusting to new modalities and striking a balance with their obligations. Time management is an important practice to meet the demands of home and work. Participants said that time management helps them to accomplish things on time. This lets them to attend school duties, do household chores, and regain energy through rest. Establishing routines through habits and practices in a set schedule helps them to utilize me efficiently. These findings are consistent with feedback from professors at my workplace. In a recent survey of online instructors, I asked several questions about their teaching experience, including the average number of hours spent each week teaching

their online course. The results were consistent, and the average number of hours, which did not include curriculum development time, set-up, or development of the course home page, was ten to twelve per week. Further research needs to be done to identify best teaching practices, pedagogical methods, and the skills associated with effective teaching online, rather than the number of hours it takes in comparison to face-to-face. Time management refers to using time effectively and productively. A synonym for efficiency, good time management makes it possible for one to make the most out of every minute (Bruner, 2019). Teachers with a heavy workload outside of the classroom must be very good at managing their time. Additionally, Razali et al. (2018) determined the relationship between time management and academic achievement of the students. The factor analysis result showed three main factors associated with time management, which can be classified as time planning, time attitudes, and time wasting.

3.3. *Educational management insights generated from teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes*—With experiences generated from the informants of this

study, it is inferable that there are mixed engagement experiences and perceptions of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. Some have found this innova-

tion in teaching and learning challenging and an essential tool in addressing the needs of the learners in this new normal shift of learning delivery. However, this might demand more capacity building for teachers, as they still have to spend time assessing and evaluating this learning modality. Teachers are adaptive to the situation and positive enough to think that this is an effective paradigm shift in education. Insights drawn from their experiences were analyzed and grouped into themes:

3.3.1. Collaboration with co-teachers—Collaboration is a key tool for creating a meaningful learning experience for all. Parents understand the needs of their children, thus making them more engaged in extending help and support. In return, teachers become more responsible for providing quality instruction to their learners. In this case, everyone is involved in designing learning opportunities. When everyone knows their roles and responsibilities, implementing the learning modality becomes organized and easy. Since the school cannot provide all the needs of teachers due to its limited resources, the gaps are filled through continuous support through community engagement and partnerships with stakeholders. The participant stated that using ICT tools has streamlined the collaboration in sharing instructional materials, increasing lesson quality, and ensuring consistent teaching standards across all of their classes. According to the participant, integrating ICT tools has enabled teachers to collaboratively track student progress, identify learning gaps, and develop targeted interventions and support strategies for students who require additional assistance. ICT tools have provided teachers with a platform to collaboratively design and implement innovative teaching strategies. The participant further described how these tools foster a creative environment and allow teachers to learn from each other's strengths and expertise. Permission from the barangays to put computer stations as hubs to gather the digitized materi-

als and put up boxes for the distribution and retrieval of printed modules was obtained. The help from external stakeholders for the other things we need that our schools cannot provide. This act of partnership is a good avenue for better understanding and responsibility. Collaboration among teachers is essential for improving the learning experience, and ICT tools play an important role in making this happen. The incorporation of ICT tools has allowed teachers to efficiently share instructional materials, track student progress, identify learning gaps, and collaborate on innovative teaching strategies. Continuous community engagement and stakeholder partnerships help to bridge resource gaps in schools, making the implementation of learning modalities more organized and efficient. According to Järvelä and Hadwin (2019), effective collaboration facilitated by technology can significantly improve educational quality by encouraging shared responsibility and ongoing professional development among educators.

3.3.2. Capacity building with co-teachers—Learning in the 21st century adheres to the use of technology. The participants are continuously familiarizing themselves with different online learning platforms. To equip themselves with the new normal education, the participants attend webinar sessions, watch video tutorials, and are mentored by peers. This allows them to widen their knowledge and develop useful skills as they design their instructional plans. Continuous learning provides growth and development of teachers as professionals, making them ready and prepared to embrace changes in the teaching landscape. Teachers play a significant role in improving the quality of education; hence, capacity building of teachers must receive top priority. The participant discovered that using ICT tools helps to build the capacity of their co-teachers and themselves by providing opportunities for continuous professional development. The participants benefited from ICT tools that enabled peer learning among co-

teachers and themselves, allowing them to share best practices and innovative teaching strategies. The integration of ICT tools has allowed participants and co-teachers to collaborate on developing and refining their digital competencies, which are critical for modern teaching. Working together and supporting one another has helped them gain confidence and proficiency in using technology to improve their teaching and learning processes. Consider the integration of online learning platforms like Google Classroom. I watch video tutorials to learn that. Reviewing the MELCs, constructing LEs and crafting activities, and exploring online learning platforms helps me a lot to gain sufficient knowledge to effectively deliver quality education in a virtual classroom. As an ICT teacher, watching videos of some common learning platforms to which students have access will be of help. The survey showed that most of the learners are only familiar with Facebook, Zoom, and Messenger. So, I send them videos on how to use other learning platforms. Attending webinars can guide teachers on how to make learning resources and materials possible. The insights gained from these experiences highlight the importance of ICT tools in teacher capacity building. Teachers improve their digital competencies and stay up to date on educational trends by participating in ongoing professional development opportunities such as webinars, video tutorials, and peer mentoring. This collaborative learning environment not only enhances individual teaching practices but also creates a supportive community in which educators can share innovative strategies and best practices. According to Admiraal et al. (2019), ongoing professional development and collaboration are required for teachers to effectively integrate technology into their instruction, resulting in better educational outcomes.

3.3.3. *Peer mentoring*—The participants mentioned that peer mentoring helps them to collaborate and share best practices. They seek

guidance and support from one another when preparing learning resources and ICT tools. Teachers sought help from co-teachers since we are dealing with the same pressure in making good outputs. Asking for help from colleagues in studying different computer applications and gathering online resources and references. I ask for assistance from those who are experts in using technology and more acquainted with integrating it into the lessons. Mentoring provides a strong support system for the holistic well-being and development of educators. As teachers embrace change, peer mentoring allows them to build confidence and nurture competence in the new normal. Teachers value the support gained from one another as a beneficial way to stay connected. Peer mentoring has been extremely beneficial to the participant and their co-teachers in terms of capacity building, as it allows for collaboration and the sharing of best practices, assisting them in managing the pressures of producing high-quality results. The participant frequently seeks assistance from colleagues who are experts in technology integration, and they report that this mentoring support system boosts their confidence and competence in adapting to the new normal in education. The participants emphasized the importance of peer mentoring in improving their ability to use ICT tools effectively in teaching. Teachers can help each other prepare learning resources and master ICT applications by working together and sharing best practices. This mutual assistance is especially useful in managing the pressures of producing high-quality educational outputs. As teachers embrace these changes, peer mentoring provides a support system that promotes connection and ongoing professional development. According to Hennessy, Haßler, and Hofmann (2019), peer mentoring in the context of ICT integration is effective in encouraging collaborative learning and professional development among teachers, resulting in better educational practices.

Fig. 5. The emerging themes of the Insights of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, which ought to look at teachers’ lived experiences of using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. It was followed by implications established in the study and future directions in the pursuit of this study.

4.1. Findings—The main objective of this study is to discover the lived experiences of teachers who use ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes. The virtual classroom is one of the most conducive venues for the delivery of quality education. This study specifically sought to discover teachers’ engagement in the classroom and the use of ICT tools to deliver meaningful learning. The researcher, through the analysis of the data gathered from the different perspectives of the informants of this study, had identified existing themes that cover up the experiences of teachers, which were classified into Inaccessibility of ICT resources, lack of effective training, and limited time in planning lessons. With the rampant issues on technologically inclined teachers, learners, and schools in general, teachers cannot separate their selves from experiencing pressure brought about by this innovation. The ICT-inclined teaching-learning process is trying to cope with the academic demands of learners nowadays. However, the overwhelming tasks,

from the preparation of instructional materials to assessment complexity, brought challenges to teachers. On the other hand, teachers were able to cope with the challenges they encountered by using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes, which were classified into themes such as self-training and support, openness to collaborate with others, self-organization, and proper time management. This helped teachers discover and adjust teaching strategies to effectively deliver quality instruction with the aid of ICT tools. Finally, the researcher drew insights from the experiences of teacher engagement in a virtual classroom that were classified into themes such as collaboration, capacity building, and peer mentoring. Collaboration is a key tool to create a meaningful learning experience for all. Teachers understand the needs of their students, thus making them more engaged in extending help and support, and in return, learners become more productive and motivated. In this case, everyone is involved in designing learning opportunities Learning in the

21st century adheres to the use of technology. The participants are continuously familiarizing themselves with different online learning platforms. To equip themselves, the participants attend webinar sessions, watch video tutorials, and are mentored by peers. This allows them to widen their knowledge and develop useful skills as they design their instructional plans. Continuous learning provides growth and development of teachers as professionals, making them ready and prepared to embrace changes in the teaching landscape. Teachers play a significant role in improving the quality of education; hence, capacity building of teachers must receive top priority. Teachers sought help from co-teachers since we are dealing with the same pressure in making good outputs. Asking for help from colleagues in studying different computer applications and gathering online resources and references is an effective way to efficiently deliver learning. Those who were experts in using technology were more acquainted with integrating it into the lessons, they can be of help to others. Mentoring provides a strong support system for educators' holistic well-being and development. As teachers embrace change, peer mentoring allows them to build confidence and nurture competence in the new normal.

4.2. Implications—In Figure 3, numerous factors impact teachers' experiences using ICT tools in the classroom, resulting in a complex web of challenges. One of these is the lack of effective training, which can hinder educators' ability to fully utilize the potential of technology. Limited access to internet connections and trouble accessing the technology itself can make it more difficult to integrate ICT tools effectively and even discourage teachers from using them at all. Meanwhile, positive effects of the experiences of teachers include interactive and engaging teaching methods, access to diverse resources, and remote learning opportunities. Figure 4 implicated that by taking the initiative to learn new technologies by themselves,

scheduling their time wisely to incorporate these tools into lessons, and working together with colleagues and experts to share best practices and knowledge, teachers can overcome the difficulties associated with implementing ICT tools in the classroom. By taking a proactive stance, they are able to stay abreast of developments in educational technology, facilitate the seamless integration of these tools into their curricula, and take advantage of the collective knowledge of educators to optimize the use of ICT tools to improve student learning. The figures reveal a two-sided story of ICT integration in classrooms. While inadequate training and technical difficulties pose challenges (Figure 3), teachers can overcome them through proactive strategies (Figure 4). These strategies include self-directed learning to acquire new skills, effective time management for smooth implementation, and collaboration with colleagues to share knowledge and best practices. By taking charge of their learning and working together, teachers can harness the potential of ICT tools to enhance student learning (Shrish et al., 2022). Teachers' adaptation to changes is indeed a must to be considered. From this generation, traditional teaching strategies no longer fit to answer the learning needs of the students, and that prompts teachers to modify their teaching pedagogy for them to be effective in bridging the gap between the needs of the learners. One of the many innovations done to give a solution to this rising phenomenon is to deliver learning in an online approach. Meanwhile, many studies have concluded that teaching using ICT tools has been an effective and essential avenue to continuing the learning experience; to wit, ICT teaching improves the professional growth of teachers of the new trend in learning delivery. This approach was used to innovate learning activities and projects. It was also an appropriate tool used by most teachers in the continuity of learning. Therefore, using ICT tools in teaching is indeed very useful to eliminate old ways of

delivering lessons. Teaching with the use of technology allows teachers to give learners a new learning experience that will teach them the knowledge and skills they need. Hence, this teaching innovation was a unique and exciting way of delivering knowledge and skills to enhance learner performance.

4.2.1. Future Directions—With the themes drawn from the experiences of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes engagement in a virtual classroom, it imposes roles and emphasis on the agency necessary to effectively perform the delivery of quality education to provide alternatives and enrich both teaching and learning experience. While the core themes are found essential to the lived experiences of teachers in using ICT tools in the teaching and learning processes, the following points are given for future consideration:

The school heads may work with the teachers in addressing the challenges they face as they migrate to 21st-century skills in learning. Division supervisors, to design programs and training regarding the necessary resources and relevant training may be provided among teachers to successfully deliver quality education. Teachers may formulate appropriate plans and implement adequate strategies to meet the demands of the teaching and learning process using ICT tools. They may adopt a growth mindset, embrace changes, and explore possibilities by getting out of their comfort zones. Future researchers could conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of ICT tools on teaching practices and student outcomes, revealing strategies for sustained educational innovation and improvement.

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